

DESIGN AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED MMC BOLT CONNECTORS

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SUMMARY: An analytic model to predict the load distribution within the shoulder area of MMC bolt connectors has been developed and verified. This model predicts, that the specimen geometry has a significant influence on the stress distribution. The theoretic stress distribution and the experiments indicate that the failure of the component occurs as soon as a critical stress level in the face of the hole has been reached. For these investigations the detected critical stress level was 550 MPa. However, this value is significantly below the values measured by tensile tests of UTS = 970 MPa. This may be due to the more complex stress field in the component than in the tensile test specimen.

The theoretic model and the experiments show, that the applicable load can be reduced by 50% and more by use of an unfavourable component geometry. A comparison of the fatigue behaviour of fibre reinforced castings to unreinforced components, machined out of a aluminium 2024 sheet, shows the improvement that can be achieved by local fibre reinforcement.

KEYWORDS: continuous fibre reinforced MMC, aluminium matrix composites, selective reinforcement, bolt connector, fatigue behaviour

INTRODUCTION

Various production processes and material combinations for CFRMs (Continuous Fibre Reinforced Metals) have been investigated in the past. Especially light weight metals such as aluminium and magnesium have attracted researchers, and in several cases, encouraging mechanical properties have been obtained [1]. One potential candidate for application is an aluminium based Zn-Mg alloy reinforced with alumina or alumina-silica fibres.

A common means for fixation of components in aeronautics and also other applications, are bolt connectors. The bolt connection of an aileron to the wing is one example. Often large scale housings are fixed to other components by rather small connectors, so that the housing may be highly stressed locally. A potential application for CFRMs can be the local reinforcement of such highly stressed areas.

Within a project funded by the EC [2] a modified investment casting process has been developed [3], which allows the production of selectively fibre-reinforced castings. The investigated test specimens have all been produced at the *Giesserei-Institut (Foundry Institute)* by this process and the testing was performed by *Aerospatiale* and *Giesserei-*

Institut. First investigations of bolt connector specimens showed unsatisfactory strength values. For better understanding an analytic model has been developed to predict the load distribution in the shoulder area of such components. This model has been confirmed by tensile tests of various specimen geometries. Additional fatigue tests showed the potential for improvement by local fibre reinforcement.

These investigations have been performed with a Al-6%Zn-1%Mg matrix, selectively reinforced by 50 vol% „Altex“ Alumina-silica fibres. The mechanical properties of the constituents and the composite are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the constituents, fibre and matrix, and of the 50 vol% unidirectionally reinforced composite ⁽¹⁾= own measurements on dog bone specimen geometry; ⁽²⁾= value given by the fibre producer).

	Al-Zn-Mg matrix ⁽¹⁾	Altex fibre ⁽²⁾	Composite ⁽¹⁾
Tensile strength [MPa]	300	1800	UTS = 970
E-Modulus [GPa]	74	210	E = 125; E _⊥ = 85
Strain to failure [%]	2 – 8	0.85	0.75 - 0.85
Density [g/cm ³]	2.95	3.3	3.1

THEORETIC LOAD DISTRIBUTION IN THE SHOULDER AREA OF BOLT CONNECTORS

All tests performed on bolt connector specimens (Fig. 1) showed a fracture in the shoulder area of the specimen. Therefore an analytic model to predict the load distribution within this area has been developed. To simplify the model some assumptions had to be made.

Fig.1: Example of selectively reinforced bolt connection geometry.

Fig.2: Typical stress-strain behaviour of unidirectional "Altex" fibre reinforced aluminium.

1. The stress-deformation correlation corresponds to the Hook's law until rupture of the specimen. The typical stress-strain behaviour of continuous ceramic fibre reinforced aluminium (Fig. 2) indicates the validity of this assumption, at least in direction of the reinforcement.

2. The stress distribution in y-direction is homogeneous.
3. A constant elongation Δl in the shoulder area of the specimen results in a peak stress of the internal fibres. This is due to the smaller circumference of internal compared to external fibres (Fig. 3).

$$\varepsilon_{ex} = \frac{2 \times \Delta l}{\pi \times R_{ex}} \quad \varepsilon_{in} = \frac{2 \times \Delta l}{\pi \times R_{in}}$$

with $R_{ex} > R_{in} \rightarrow \varepsilon_{in} > \varepsilon_{ex} \xrightarrow{\text{Hook's law}} \sigma_{in} > \sigma_{ex}$

4. The bolt creates compression in the face of the hole, which results in a further relaxation of the external fibres Δl_{\perp} . This is due to elastic deformations transverse to the fibre orientation (Fig. 4).

$$2 \times \Delta l_{\perp} = \pi \times R_{ex} - \pi \times R_{ex'} = \pi (R_{ex} - R_{ex'})$$

$$\Delta l_{\perp} = \frac{1}{2} \pi \times \lambda_{\perp} \tag{1}$$

Δl_{\perp} is given as soon as λ_{\perp} has been determined.

Fig.3: Linear elongation Δl in the shoulder area of the specimen

Fig.4: Relaxation Δl_{\perp} caused by compression in the face of the hole

5. Presuming the validity of Hook's law also transverse to the fibre orientation, it follows:

$$\sigma_{\perp}(r) = \varepsilon_{\perp}(r) \times E_{\perp} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \varepsilon_{\perp}(r) = \frac{\sigma_{\perp}(r)}{E_{\perp}} \tag{2}$$

6. A linear decrease of σ_{\perp} has been assumed, showing a maximum at the face of the hole and dropping to zero at the outside. This means:

$$\sigma_{\perp}(R_{in}) = \frac{2N}{(R_{ex} + R_{in}) \times a} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{\perp}(R_{ex}) = 0$$

Herewith the stress $\sigma_{\perp}(r)$ transverse to the fibres results to:

$$\sigma_{\perp}(r) = \frac{2N}{(R_{ex}^2 - R_{in}^2) \times a} (R_{ex} - r) \quad (3)$$

The strain at the position r is given by the quotient of the infinitesimal relaxation $d\lambda_{\perp}$ versus the infinitesimal radius dr .

$$\varepsilon_{\perp}|_r = \frac{d\lambda_{\perp}}{dr}$$

In combination with Eqn 2 we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\lambda_{\perp}}{dr} &= \frac{\sigma_{\perp}(r)}{E_{\perp}} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad d\lambda_{\perp} = \frac{\sigma_{\perp}(r)}{E_{\perp}} dr \\ \lambda_{\perp}(r) &= \int_{R_{in}}^r \frac{\sigma_{\perp}(r)}{E_{\perp}} dr \\ \lambda_{\perp}(r) &= \frac{2N}{E_{\perp}(R_{ex}^2 - R_{in}^2)a} \left[R_{ex}(r - R_{in}) - \frac{1}{2}(r^2 - R_{in}^2) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The stress distribution in the shoulder area parallel to the fibres $\sigma_{\parallel}(r)$ can be calculated by overlapping the two effects, the linear elongation Δl in the shoulder area of the specimen and the relaxation Δl_{\perp} caused by compression in the face of the hole.

$$\sigma_{\parallel}(r) = \frac{2[\Delta l - \Delta l_{\perp}(r)]}{\pi \cdot r} E_{\parallel}$$

With Eqn 1 and 4 it follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\parallel}(r) &= \frac{2\Delta l - \pi \cdot \lambda_{\perp}(r)}{\pi \cdot r} E_{\parallel} \\ \sigma_{\parallel}(r) &= \frac{2\Delta l}{\pi \cdot r} E_{\parallel} - \frac{2N}{(R_{ex}^2 - R_{in}^2)a} \cdot \frac{E_{\parallel}}{E_{\perp}} \cdot \frac{1}{r} \cdot \left[R_{ex}(r - R_{in}) - \frac{1}{2}(r^2 - R_{in}^2) \right] \end{aligned}$$

It has to be considered that there is no relaxation of the fibres in the face of the hole.

$$\sigma_{\parallel}(r = R_{in}) = \sigma_{in} = \frac{2\Delta l}{\pi \cdot R_{in}} E_{\parallel}$$

Herewith we get:

$$\sigma_{\parallel}(r) = \sigma_{in} \cdot \frac{R_{in}}{r} - \frac{2N}{(R_{ex}^2 - R_{in}^2)a} \cdot \frac{E_{\parallel}}{E_{\perp}} \cdot \left[R_{ex} - \frac{1}{2}r + \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{R_{in}^2}{2} - R_{ex} \cdot R_{in} \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

The integral of the stress $\sigma_{\parallel}(r)$ via the width of the shoulders must be in equilibrium with the load N applied by the bolt.

$$N = 2 \cdot \int_{R_{in}}^{R_{ex}} \sigma_{\parallel}(r) \cdot a \cdot dr$$

With Eqn 5 it follows:

$$\sigma_{in} = \frac{N}{2 \cdot a \cdot R_{in} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}}\right)} \left\{ 1 + 2 \frac{E_{II}}{E_{\perp}} \left[\frac{1}{2} + \left(1 + \ln\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}}\right) \right) \frac{\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} - 1\right)}{\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} + 1\right)} - \ln\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}}\right) \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}}\right)^2}{\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}}\right)^2 - 1} \right] \right\} \quad (6)$$

Inserting Eqn 6 into Eqn 5 and after some additional transformations, we get:

$$\sigma_{II}(r) = \left\{ \left[\frac{1}{2 \ln\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}}\right)} + \frac{E_{II}}{E_{\perp}} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2 \ln\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}}\right)} + \frac{1}{\ln\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}}\right)} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} - 1\right)}{\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} + 1\right)} \right) \right] \frac{1}{r} + \left[\frac{E_{II}}{E_{\perp}} \right] \cdot r - \left[\frac{2 \left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}} \cdot \frac{E_{II}}{E_{\perp}}\right)}{R_{in} \cdot \left(\left(\frac{R_{ex}}{R_{in}}\right)^2 - 1\right)} \right] \right\} \frac{N}{a}$$

The final structure of the equation is:

$$\sigma_{II}(r) = \left\{ A \cdot \frac{1}{r} + B \cdot r - C \right\} \cdot \frac{N}{a}$$

Obviously the specimen geometry, especially the quotient R_{ex}/R_{in} , has a decisive influence on the stress distribution in the shoulder area. The anisotropy of the material is represented by the quotient of the elastic modulus in fibre direction and transverse to it E_{II}/E_{\perp} . Furthermore the load applied N and the specimen geometry, represented by the width a and the internal radius R_{in} , influence the stress values.

For validation of the above equation three different specimen geometries have been produced and tested. The theoretic stress distribution for these geometries are shown in Fig.7.

TENSILE TEST RESULTS

The first specimen geometry investigated is shown in Fig.5 and has been produced and tested within a BritEuRam project. For comparison specimens of the same geometry have been machined out of a 2024 aluminium sheet. The tests showed that the tensile strength of the 2024 specimens is 390 MPa in average compared to 189 MPa for the composite (Fig.8).

The starting point for the theoretical and practical investigations on the influence of the specimen geometry on tensile strength, was to explain the low tensile strength values detected with geometry 1. The follow up investigations have been performed as university study in cooperation of *Institut für Leichtbau (Institute for light weight structures)* and *Giesserei Institut*. To facilitate the investigation and to minimise the material required, three small geometries have been selected (Table 2), showing always the same cross section of the shoulder area. With these geometries a significant variation of the relation R_{ex}/R_{in} has been achieved. The tensile tests have been performed on a servohydraulic test device. The applied load has been increased with a step width of 1000 N starting from zero until failure of the specimen. Additionally the strain of the external fibres have been recorded with strain gauges (Fig. 6). The average tensile strength, the external fibre stress and the resulting theoretic stress distribution are shown in Fig.7.

Fig 5: First investigated bolt connection geometry. For reinforcement the fibres are wound around a hole.

Table 2: Geometries, average tensile strength and external fibre stress values of the three small bolt connectors (see Fig.1).

	Specimen geometry		
	small	medium	large
a [mm]	4	4	4
H [mm]	80	80	80
R _{in} [mm]	2	3	6
R _{ex} [mm]	4.5	5.5	8.8
A = 2a*(R _{ex} -R _{in}) [mm ²]	20	20	20
R _{ex} / R _{in}	2.25	1.83	1.42
N [N]	4400	5500	8000
σ _{ex}	90	46	320

Fig. 6: Small specimen geometry equipped with strain gauges after tensile test.

Fig.7: Average tensile strength, detected by the load cell of the servohydraulic test equipment, calculated stress distribution in the shoulder area of the specimen and average tensile stress of the external fibres, measured by strain gauges, for the three investigated geometries.

From Fig.7 it can be seen that the geometry has a significant influence on the load distribution and that with increasing R_{ex}/R_{in} ratio the average tensile strength decreases significantly. Even though the average tensile strength of the small specimen is much lower than of the large one, the peak stress in the face of the hole for all three specimens is similar. This indicates that once the critical stress level for the composite has been reached, a sudden failure of the specimen occurs. However, the peak level (550 MPa) of the bolt connector specimens is significantly lower than the values detected by tensile tests (970 MPa). The geometry 1 specimen has a even worse ratio of $R_{ex}/R_{in} = 2.42$ and therefore the average tensile strength is very low.

FATIGUE TEST RESULTS

Fatigue tests have been performed on specimens of geometry 1, reinforced with 50 vol.% „Altex“ fibres, made of the same Al-Zn-Mg alloy as used for tensile test specimens. Furthermore five components have been machined from 2024 T351 plates in order to compare the properties of fibre reinforced cast parts to those of a conventional wrought alloy, frequently used on aerospace structures. All the specimens have been tested on a MTS machine. Fatigue tests were conducted at $R = 0,1$ under a frequency of 10 Hertz. The test results are shown in Fig.8.

Fig.8: Tensile and fatigue test results of fibre reinforced castings and unreinforced machined specimen of geometry 1.

CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The advantageous tensile properties of the composite (970 MPa) could not be transferred to the bolt connector geometry. This can be due to the more complex stress field in the component than in the tensile test specimen. The bolt creates compression transverse to the orientation of the fibre reinforcement. This effect is overlapped by an additionally tensile loading of the composite in fibre direction. Both stresses have their maximum in the face of the hole.

The specimen geometry influences the stress distribution in the shoulder area significantly. Compared to unreinforced aluminium the composite shows only limited stress relaxation's in the shoulder area, especially in the face of the hole, which results in a sudden failure of the component, as soon as a critical peak stress-level has been reached. This can be explained by the characteristic stress-strain of the ceramic fibre reinforcement, which is almost linear until failure. Therefore the tensile strength values of the composite component are rather low and a favourable geometry has a R_{ex} / R_{in} ratio close to 1. For unfavourable geometries the external sections of the component remain almost unloaded.

The fatigue tests show that, even though the tensile strength values of composite geometry 1 specimens are much lower than of unreinforced 2024, the fatigue behaviour can significantly be improved. Under a stress of 150 MPa, both materials present the same behaviour and for lower stresses longer fatigue lives have been observed on the composite. These results confirm the high fatigue potential of fibre reinforced aluminium castings.

There are two possibilities to reach a favourable stress distribution in the shoulder area of bolt connectors:

1. To design the component with a R_{ex}/R_{in} ratio close to 1
2. With increasing radius r a gradual increase of the composite stiffness would homogenise the stress distribution.

A gradual increase represents the theoretical optimum, but would be very difficult to realise. Therefore a step by step increase is more realistic. Specimens of geometry 1 are in preparation showing an unreinforced section in the centre followed up by an alumina-silica "Altex" reinforcement and a pure alumina "Nextel 610" reinforcement of the external section. Test results will be presented at the conference.

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